

I. AXIAL CODING REPRESENTATIONS

Fig. 1. "Positives" relationships in the Brazilian GSECO scenario.

Fig. 2. "Negatives" relationships in the Brazilian GSECO scenario.

Fig. 3. "Opportunities" relationships in the Brazilian GSECO scenario.